

Agro2Circular

D8.9 – Contribution to standardization (Draft)

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Table of contents

1	List of abbreviations	5
2	Executive summary <abstract>	6
3	Standardization Strategy	7
3.1	Definition of the strategy	7
3.1.1	First contact with the standardization technical committees	7
3.1.2	Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees	8
3.1.3	Standardization process	8
3.2	Implementation	10
3.2.1	Contact with the standardization technical committees	10
3.2.2	Standardization process	10
3.2.3	Summary of the implementation	11
4	Contact with technical committees	12
4.1	First contact with the standardization technical committees	12
4.2	Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees	15
5	Conclusions	17

1 List of abbreviations

CEN European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization
CWA Workshop Agreements
ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute
IEC International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO International standardization organization
SC Subcommittee
TC Technical committee
TS Technical Specifications
TR Technical Reports
WG Working group

2 Executive summary <abstract>

This D.8.9, “Contribution to standardization (Draft)”, defines the strategy for the Agro2Circular contribution to on-going and future standardization. It includes the steps towards a successful contribution to standardization, the actions for its implementation and a tentative schedule. Also, this D.8.9 describes the selection of the relevant TCs to contact with and the first contact effectively made with these TCs.

This D. 8.9 will be updated with the progress and outcomes of the different actions resulting in the final version of D.8.10 at M34.

The schedule of the actions described in this document is open to changes according to the progress of the A2C Project and the update of the standardization landscape.

3 Standardization Strategy

3.1 Definition of the strategy

The contribution to standardization of Agro2Circular is based in the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees and in the initiation of a standardization process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in the next figure:

Figure 1 – Agro2Circular Strategy for the contribution to standardization

The different steps are explained below.

3.1.1 First contact with the standardization technical committees

The objective of this first contact is to raise awareness about Agro2Circular among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at European/international level are present in these committees, so the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback will be asked to gather any view, opinion or advice about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Additionally, this first contact will be useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardization process, moreover this first step will ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardization committee.

3.1.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the selected technical committees. Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: the impact/relevance for Agro2Circular of the standardization works within the committees and the feasibility of initiating a standardization process within a standardization committee (versus initiating the standardization process within a workshop created ad hoc, details are given below). The ways of interaction of the A2C project with the TCs can include:

- Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardization committees. This allows to detect the initiation of standardization works that can be relevant for Agro2Circular and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardization activity resulting in updates of the D8.8.
- Further contact with the standardization committees to update the progress of Agro2Circular. This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardization process.
- The participation of one or more Agro2Circular partners in the standardization technical committees. Standardization is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardization Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardization committee and it is valuable if the standardization process is going to be initiated within the standardization committee.
- The establishment of a formal liaison of Agro2Circular with the standardization committees. It is recommended only when the work of the standardization committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected.

3.1.3 Standardization process

The main objective of the standardization activities in Agro2Circular is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners the feasible results to go through a standardization process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardization shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and intellectual property rights) and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardization committees):

The **different options for A2C to contribute to standardization** can include:

- Development of a new standard within a standardization workshop. A standardization workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardization committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures are faster and more flexible. A standardization workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardization committees or when the standard does not fit into the committees' work program. If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardization committee, it shall be informed and it shall allow to launch the standardization workshop.

In the European environment, the standardization workshop is named CEN-CENELEC Workshop and the corresponding developed standard is called CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA). The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for R&I projects.

- Standardization within a standardization committee. To standardize the Agro2Circular results within a standardization committee may be interesting or needed. The possible scenarios are:
 - a. New standard development within a standardization committee. This option applies to new standards with scopes covered by an existing standardization committee, which decides to include it in its work program. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardization committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardization committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.
 - b. Contribute to an on-going standard. As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardization landscape, it may be found that the Agro2Circular results are covered by a standard under development but that these results do not fit in the current standard draft. Gaps in standards may be found in both: 1- standards that are being developed from a new initiative and 2. standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.
 - c. Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review. The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardization committee.

- d. Outline of a future standard. Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardization (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

3.2 Implementation

The actions and approach to be performed for the implementation of each step of the strategy are detailed below.

3.2.1 Contact with the standardization technical committees

3.2.1.1 First contact with the standardization technical committees

For the first contact implementation, it is necessary to previously select the relevant standardization committees to contact with, among those that were identified in the standardization landscape related to the Agro2Circular project (D8.8).

Also it is necessary to define the information to share with these TCs, considering the potential interest of the stakeholders integrating the TCs and the degree of confidentiality of the information.

3.2.1.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

The monitoring of the relevant standardization activity will be continuous during the duration of A2C project but tentative formal dates can be set:

- M13 (prior to the first contact with the standardization committees)
- M20 (to be aligned with the needs of the standardization process)
- M28 (to be aligned with the needs of the standardization process)

The standardization committees included in Table 1 will be updated with the relevant progress in A2C, if this is considered valuable by the committees. This will be done by updating the report/information provided in the first contacts and, at the same time, keeping open the possibility of having a face-to-face interaction (e.g., attending a meeting of the standardization committee if feasible). The implication of the Coordinator/Partners will be needed for presenting A2C technical details to the committee.

Further interactions with the standardization committees (participation of members of A2C in committees and the consideration of a project liaison) will be determined as a function of the interaction with the technical committees and the standardization approach.

3.2.2 Standardization process

Based on the standardizable A2C results, on the standardization landscape, on the interaction with the standardization committees and on the progress of the project, the most suitable roadmap among the options described in 4.1.3 will be selected and conducted.

A standardization A2C session for the standardizable results identification and the roadmap selection is foreseen. This session could take place during a project meeting. A tentative date for this standardization session is M18.

The standardization process is considered very valuable for the market uptake of the A2C results and for the impact of the project beyond the financing period.

3.2.3 Summary of the implementation

The summary of the tentative dates and the actors involved is included in the following table:

Table 2 – Summary of the actions in the strategy for the A2C contribution to standardization

Action	Actors involved	Month
First contacts with the standardization committees in Table 1	UNE (content of the communication with Coordinator agreed)	M12
Updates on the standardization landscape	UNE	Continuous but formally at M12, M20, M28
Provision of updated report/information to the standardization committees identified in Table 1	UNE (content of the communication with Coordinator agreed)	When convenient
Face to face interaction with the relevant standardization committees	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When convenient
Standardization A2C session	UNE	M18
Standardization process	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M18-M36

4 Contact with technical committees

4.2 First contact with the standardization technical committees

For the “first contact” implementation, the relevant standardization committees to contact were selected among those that were identified in the standardization landscape related to the Agro2Circular project (D8.8).

The selection was performed on the basis of possible standardization outcomes from A2C. The main standardizable innovative outcomes were identified mainly in the following areas:

- General waste and biowaste
- Plastics: plastics recycling, environmental aspects, bio-based and biodegradable plastics, and thermoplastic films for use in agriculture.

Regarding the rest of technical areas identified in D8.8 (“Circular economy”, “LCA”, “Food, Cosmetics, Extracts”, “Biotechnology” and “Information technology”), in principle standardizable A2C outcomes are not foreseen, or the scopes of the corresponding TCs do not match with the possible A2C outcomes (The consideration of these other TCs and the corresponding selected standards will be valuable in terms of compliance with established requirements and in terms of information for the A2C R&D developments).

Accordingly, the standardization committees proposed for contacting with, for the objectives described in 4.1.1, are indicated in the following Table:

Technical area	Standardization Technical Committees
General waste and biowaste	CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices
Plastics	CEN/TC 249 Plastics: CEN/TC 249/WG 7 Thermoplastic films for use in agriculture CEN/TC 249/WG 9 Characterization of degradability CEN/TC 249/WG 11 Plastics/Plastics recycling

Table 1 – Identification of standardization committees to be contacted

The information to disseminate to the TCs avoiding any confidential content was agreed between the A2C coordinator and the partner UNE (Spanish Association for Standardization).

The following information was shared by email with the secretary of the CEN/TC 444:

Dear XXXX

I'm addressing you on behalf of the H2020 project Agro2Circular which aim is *A2C is to boost the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from fruit and vegetables, and multilayer plastic films) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food, cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation.*

As part of this project, under the responsibility of UNE (Spanish standardization body) representing CEN/CENELEC in Agro2Circular, specific standardization activities are included to:

- Ensure compatibility with existing technologies by the identification of relevant existing standards.
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardization technical committees.
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardization in the field.

The link with CEN/TC 444 comes from the objective of the Project of improving the upcycling of agri-food wastes that pass also through the better characterization of the wastes considering their final destination and applications. Standards from CEN/TC 444 dealing with characterization of waste and biowaste were identified as relevant for the project.

For your information, other CEN and ISO TCs will also be contacted with this information.

The objective of this contact is, on the one hand, to raise awareness on the project to these TCs and gather feedback on any suggestion, question or comment. On the other hand, it is intended in the second half of the project the Agro2Circular contribution to standardization from the selected/standardizable project results. Depending on several factors such as the nature of these results and the standardization landscape at the corresponding moment, this contribution to standardization may be oriented to generate new pre-standards (Workshop Agreements) or to participate at TC level.

Please, find attached a brief summary containing more information about Agro2Circular and also the webpage here: <https://agro2circular.eu/>. Feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and results of the project. Now the project is nearly 1/2 progressed and we would be very grateful if you could give us feedback regarding the interest of this project for the activity of the TC. Additionally, any suggestion, question or comment related to the project would be very useful.

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kinds of contact (a dedicated telco, attending a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward to your reply.

Best regards,

Project manager R&I
Spanish Association for Standardization – UNE

The following information was shared by email with the secretary of the CEN/TC 249:

Dear XXXX

I'm addressing you on behalf of the H2020 project Agro2Circular which aim is *to boost the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from fruit and vegetables, and multilayer plastic films) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food, cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation.*

As part of this project, under the responsibility of UNE (Spanish standardization body) representing CEN/CENELEC in Agro2Circular, specific standardization activities are included to:

- Ensure compatibility with existing technologies by the identification of relevant existing standards.
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardization technical committees and
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardization in the field.

CEN/TC 249 is closely related to the Agro2Circular scope, and indeed many of the standards of this TC were identified as very relevant for the project, including standards related to plastics recycling, environmental aspects, bio-based and biodegradable plastics, and thermoplastic films for use in agriculture.

Also for your information, other CEN TCs will be also contacted with this information.

The objective of this contact is, on the one hand, to raise awareness on the project to this TCs and gather feedback on any suggestion, question or comment. On the other hand, it is intended in the second half of the project the Agro2Circular contribution to standardization from the selected/standardizable project results. Depending on several factors such as the nature of these results and the standardization landscape at the corresponding moment, this contribution to standardization may be oriented to generate new pre-standards (Workshop Agreements).

At this moment, Agro2Circular experts are already participating or managing to join different WG (WG 7, 9 and 11), related also to the on-going EC standardization request.

Please, find attached a brief summary containing more information about Agro2Circular and also the webpage here: <https://agro2circular.eu/>. Feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and

results of the project. Now the project is nearly 1/2 progressed and any suggestion, question or comment related with the project would be very useful.

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kind of contact (a dedicated telco, attending a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward to your reply.
Best regards,

Project manager R&D
Spanish Association for Standardization – UNE

4.3 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

The monitoring of the relevant standardization activity was made so far, and it will be continued during the whole duration of the project.

As a result of the monitoring, the European Commission standardization request to CEN/CENELEC as regards plastics recycling and recycled plastics in support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy was identified

The coordinators of the A2C project (CETEC) jointly with the partner UNE (Spanish Association for Standardization) have studied possible options to participate in the new standardization developments foreseen in the frame of the CE standardization request.

It has been considered as relevant for maximizing the transfer of the A2C outcomes to the industry the participation of CETEC in the following working groups, being involved in the CE standardization request:

- CEN/TC 249/WG 9 Bio-based and biodegradable plastics
- CEN/TC 249/WG 11 Plastics recycling
- CEN/TC 261/SC 4/WG 10 Design for recycling for plastic packaging products

The participation in these working groups could be carried out via the membership of CETEC in the spanish national mirror committee CTN-UNE 53.

In addition, the A2C partner SOLPLAST is participating in the following CEN working groups:

- CEN/TC 249/WG 7 - Thermoplastic films for use in agriculture
- CEN/TC 249/WG 26 - Agricultural Plastic products – Design for recycling, use, removal, collection and recycling
- CEN/TC 249/WG 11 - Plastics recycling

Pedro P. Diez (SOLPLAST) has attended the following meetings of these working groups:

- CEN/TC 249/WG 7. 21/03/2022. Dealing with the needs for the modification of standards about agricultural films with the aim to include the use of recycled products in these materials.
- CEN/TC 249/WG 11 08/09/2022 and 30/11/2022. Dealing with the revision of all standards about plastics recycling, studying existing developments at national level, and possible agreements with other standardization organizations.

5 Conclusions

The draft standardization strategy for the A2C contribution to standardization has been developed. The relevant standardization technical committees for initiating a contact have been selected. The information to share in these contacts has been agreed. The first contact has been effectively made. The participation of A2C partners in CEN working groups is being managed, regarding specifically to the participation of A2C experts in the EC standardization request to CEN regards plastics recycling and recycled plastics. This deliverable will be updated along the whole project duration, including the feedback obtained from the TCs contacted and the A2C contributions to standardization.

